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UNDER THE SURFACE: INTERPRETING TECHNICAL METADATA AS ARCHIVAL NARRATIVE

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RESEARCH AIMS

- To examine how technical metadata support the analysis of born-digital literary archives.
- To explore metadata as archival narratives – revealing creative, temporal, and authorial layers.

CONTEXT

THE CHALLENGE OF BORN-DIGITAL LITERARY ARCHIVES

- Personal digital documents are fluid, easily modifiable, and distributed across multiple devices
- Subject to rapid technological obsolescence
- Require new archival methodologies beyond traditional practices

PAVIA ARCHIVI DIGITALI (PAD)

- Italy's first dedicated research initiative (2009) within the Centro Manoscritti, University of Pavia
- Development of Digital Preservation Workflow (DPW) software: a tool for the digital archival processing, from acquisition and preservation to access and consultation.

WHY TECHNICAL METADATA MATTER

TECHNICAL METADATA AUTOMATICALLY EXTRACTED VIA APACHE TIKA AND EXIFTOOL:

Include:

- File format, MIME type, encoding, language
- Author, title, creation & modification dates
- Editing time, revision count, company info

SERVE BOTH ARCHIVAL AND PHILOLOGICAL PURPOSES:

- Provenance and authenticity
- Reconstruction of writing processes

CASE STUDIES

CONTRAST CURATED VS. UNFILTERED ARCHIVES

SILVIA AVALLONE (BIELLA, 1984)

- Donation: Summer 2011
- 69 files, 8 folders, 29.74 MB
- Timeframe: October 2007 – July 2011
- Author-curated corpus
- Formats: PDF, JPEG, DOC, DOCX

PAOLO DI PAOLO (ROMA, 1983)

- Donation: 2015
- 3,119 files, 5.43 GB
- Timeframe: 2000–2014
- Near-complete device transfer
- Formats: DOC, DOCX, PDF, MP3, MP4, JPEG

TEMPORAL DIMENSIONS

THE ENIGMA OF DOCUMENT DATING: SILVIA AVALLONE'S NOVELS

Problem Identified: Significant discrepancies between:

- Filesystem metadata
- Automatically extracted metadata (Tika and ExifTool)

Implications: Document dating requires contextual interpretation and critical analysis

Observation:

Extracted modification dates differ from filesystem timestamps by exactly 2 hours

<i>File name</i>	<i>File system modification data</i>	<i>Tika (dcterms:created)</i>	<i>Exiftool(Create Date)</i>	<i>Tika (dcterms:modified)</i>	<i>Exiftool (Modify Date)</i>
Acciaio – Dattiloscritto del 18 settembre2009.doc	7/19/2011 15:10	2008-05-29T12:11:00Z	2008:05:29 12:11:00	2011-07-19T13:10:00Z	2011:07:19 13:10:00
Il libro dei vent'anni.doc	7/19/2011 15:10	2006-12-19T21:44:00Z	2006:12:19 21:44:00	2011-07-19T13:11:00Z	2011:07:19 13:11:00
Alcune ragazze lo sanno.docx	7/19/2011 15:10	2010-11-06T09:05:00Z	2010:11:06 09:05:00Z	2011-07-19T13:23:00Z	2011:07:19 13:23:00Z

TEMPORAL DIMENSIONS

THE ENIGMA OF DOCUMENT DATING: SILVIA AVALLONE'S NOVELS

EXPLANATION: THE TIME ZONE ISSUE

- **Apache Tika/ExifTool:** Normalize to UTC (Coordinated Universal Time)
- **File system (FAT):** Records local system time
- **CEST (Central European Summer Time):** UTC+2 in Italy during summer

**THE 2-HOUR DIFFERENCE CONFIRMS FILES WERE MODIFIED
IN SUMMER 2011 WITH COMPUTER SET TO CEST**

TEMPORAL DIMENSIONS

THE WRITING PROCESS: PAOLO DI PAOLO'S NOVEL "DOVE ERAVATE TUTTI"

- First draft: storia degli anni senza nome.doc – Nov 2009
- Progressive drafts: 2009 → early 2011
- Final versions: DOVE ERAVATE TUTTI def maggio 2011.doc and aggiunte Dove eravate tutti.do
- Writing process spanned ~18 months (Nov 2009 – Jun 2011)
- Metadata consistency between Tika and ExifTool confirms document chronology (and the Time Zone Issue +1) Indicates iterative composition and multiple revision stages
- Value for Philological Inquiry: Metadata enables partial reconstruction of the writing process and subsequent revisions

<i>File name</i>	<i>File system modification data</i>	<i>Tika (dcterms:created)</i>	<i>Exiftool(Create Date)</i>	<i>Tika (dcterms:modified)</i>	<i>Exiftool (Modify Date)</i>
storia degli anni senza nome.doc	12/4/2009 15:48	2009-11-25T08:42:00Z	2009:11:25 08:42:00	2009-12-04T14:47:00Z	2009:12:04 14:47:00
crescere con Berlusconi.doc	12/30/2009 0:27	2009-12-29T17:34:00Z	2009:12:29 17:34:00	2009-12-29T23:27:00Z	2009:12:29 23:27:00
la cosa meno seria.doc	11/10/2010 10:08	2010-11-10T09:07:40Z	2010:11:10 09:07:40	2010-11-10T09:07:40Z	0
dov'eravate.doc	1/26/2011 11:24	2010-02-15T13:18:00Z	2010:02:15 13:18:00	2011-01-26T10:24:00Z	2011:01:26 10:24:00
dov'eravate tutti dic010.doc	3/3/2011 19:44	2010-02-15T13:18:00Z	2010:02:15 13:18:00	2011-03-03T18:44:00Z	2011:03:03 18:44:00
aggiunte.doc	3/15/2011 11:03	2011-03-15T09:51:00Z	2011:03:15 09:51:00	2011-03-15T10:03:00Z	2011:03:15 10:03:00
DOVE ERAVATE TUTTI 2011.doc	3/28/2011 19:46	2011-03-03T18:53:00Z	2011:03:03 18:53:00	2011-03-28T17:46:00Z	2011:03:28 17:46:00
incipit Paolo Di Paolo.doc	4/4/2011 13:32	2011-04-04T11:17:00Z	2011:04:04 11:17:00	2011-04-04T11:32:00Z	2011:04:04 11:32:00
DOVE ERAVATE TUTTI def maggio	5/18/2011 16:52	2011-05-16T14:37:00Z	2011:05:16 14:37:00	2011-05-18T14:52:00Z	2011:05:18 14:52:00
aggiunte Dove eravate tutti.doc	6/24/2011 23:27	2011-06-10T14:29:00Z	2011:06:10 14:29:00	2011-06-24T21:27:00Z	2011:06:24 21:27:00

AUTHORIAL DIMENSIONS

METADATA DISCREPANCIES: DC:CREATOR OFTEN DIFFERS FROM THE ACTUAL AUTHOR

Causes:

- Shared/institutional devices
- Collaborative writing
- File reuse or transfer over time

SILVIA AVALLONE

- 4 files list Ritanna Armeni as creator
- Indicates possible collaboration (Dizionario Femminile)
- No published text → likely document reuse/templates

Archival Implications:

- Challenge to accurate authorship attribution
- Need for critical interpretation of metadata

PAOLO DI PAOLO

- dc:creator shows other names or co-authors
- Texts by others under his metadata → shared device / collaborative process
- Dual-name entries → manual editing in Microsoft Word

TEXTUAL DIMENSIONS

TITLES AND DENOMINATIONS

dc:title (Apache Tika) / Title (ExifTool) → reflects the document's title property but it can be manually edited and often diverges from the file name.

May represent:

- official title
- provisional/working title
- first written line (in older .doc files)

Interpretive Value:

Major title–filename discrepancies → suggest file reuse or template creation.

Avallone archive: limited interpretive relevance (titles not tied to textual development).

Di Paolo archive: dc:title aligns closely with content → valuable for tracing text evolution.

TEXTUAL DIMENSIONS

DUPLICATIONS

- Di Paolo archive: numerous duplicate files → low curatorial filtering.
- Avallone archive: no duplicates → selective pre-donation curation.
- Duplication patterns reveal:
 - • author's document management habits
 - • degree of archival mediation before donation.
- DPW software employs:
 - • file hash analysis → detects identical files.
 - • similarity index algorithms → identify near-duplicates & textual variants.

REVISIONS

- The number of revisions or saves has a significance only when examined with other metadata:
- Creation Date
- Last Modification Date
- Total Editing Time
- Only meaningful when correlated across fields.
- Reveals editing dynamics and workflow patterns.

CONCLUSION

Technical metadata as a valuable resource:

- ✓ Accurate archival description
- ✓ In-depth philological inquiry
- ✓ Reconstruction of creative processes
- ✓ Documentation of authorial behaviors

Interpretative Challenges

Necessitates a critical, contextual interpretation

Tools such as Apache Tika and ExifTool are indispensable but require cross-verification of results

Understanding born-digital archives demands integration of:

Archival science; Computational philology; Digital forensics; Humanistic expertise to navigate the complexity of digital documentality and ensure responsible preservation and interpretation of literary heritage

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THANK YOU

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